

Participante: Miguel Angel Hidalgo Reyes

Instalación

1.1.1 Crear la cuenta de usuario dspace


```
miahreyes@debianmhr: ~  
miahreyes@debianmhr:~$ useradd -c "Repositorio de DSpace" -d /home/dspace -m -s /bin/bash dspace  
bash: useradd: orden no encontrada  
miahreyes@debianmhr:~$ sudo useradd -c "Repositorio de DSpace" -d /home/dspace -m -s /bin/bash dspace  
[sudo] contraseña para miahreyes:  
miahreyes@debianmhr:~$ sudo passwd dspace  
Nueva contraseña:  
Vuelva a escribir la nueva contraseña:  
passwd: contraseña actualizada correctamente  
miahreyes@debianmhr:~$
```

Crear la carpeta software para instalar el backend


```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/software/dspace9  
miahreyes@debianmhr:~$ su - dspace  
Contraseña:  
dspace@debianmhr:~$ mkdir software  
dspace@debianmhr:~$ cd software  
dspace@debianmhr:~/software$ mkdir dspace9  
dspace@debianmhr:~/software$ cd dspace9  
dspace@debianmhr:~/software/dspace9$ ls -l  
total 0  
dspace@debianmhr:~/software/dspace9$
```

1.1.2 Software copiado

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/software/dspace9
miahreyes@debianmhr:~$ su - dspace
Contraseña:
dspace@debianmhr:~$ mkdir software
dspace@debianmhr:~$ cd software
dspace@debianmhr:~/software$ mkdir dspace9
dspace@debianmhr:~/software$ cd dspace9
dspace@debianmhr:~/software/dspace9$ ls -l
total 0
dspace@debianmhr:~/software/dspace9$ ls
apache-ant-1.10.15-bin.zip  apache-tomcat-10.1.30.tar.gz  DSpace-dspace-9.1.zip  jdk-17_linux-x64_bin.tar.gz
apache-maven-3.8.8-bin.zip  dspace-angular-dspace-9.1.zip  GeoLite2-City.mmdb  solr-9.9.0.tgz
dspace@debianmhr:~/software/dspace9$
```

Crear carpeta java dentro del directorio /usr

```
miahreyes@debianmhr: /usr
miahreyes@debianmhr:~$ cd /usr
miahreyes@debianmhr:/usr$ ls
bin  games  include  lib  lib64  libexec  local  sbin  share  src
miahreyes@debianmhr:/usr$ mkdir java
mkdir: no se puede crear el directorio «java»: Permiso denegado
miahreyes@debianmhr:/usr$ sudo mkdir java
[sudo] contraseña para miahreyes:
miahreyes@debianmhr:/usr$ ls
bin  games  include  java  lib  lib64  libexec  local  sbin  share  src
miahreyes@debianmhr:/usr$ chown dspace:dspace java
chown: cambiando el propietario de 'java': Operación no permitida
miahreyes@debianmhr:/usr$ sudo chown dspace:dspace java
miahreyes@debianmhr:/usr$
```

Descomprimir el paquete JDK

```
miahreyes@debianmhr: /usr/java
root@debianmhr: /usr/java$ sudo su
root@debianmhr: /usr/java# gunzip -c /home/dspace/software/dspace9/jdk-17_linux-x64_bin.tar.gz | tar xvf -
jdk-17.0.5/LICENSE
jdk-17.0.5/README
jdk-17.0.5/bin/jar
jdk-17.0.5/bin/jarsigner
jdk-17.0.5/bin/java
jdk-17.0.5/bin/javac
jdk-17.0.5/bin/javadoc
jdk-17.0.5/bin/javap
jdk-17.0.5/bin/jcmm
jdk-17.0.5/bin/jconsole
jdk-17.0.5/bin/jdb
jdk-17.0.5/bin/jdeprscan
jdk-17.0.5/bin/jdeps
```

Descomprimir los siguientes paquetes

```
miahreyes@debianmhr: /usr/java
root@debianmhr: /usr/java# ls -l
total 20
drwxr-xr-x 6 root root 4096 ago 25 2024 apache-ant-1.10.15
drwxr-xr-x 6 root root 4096 mar 8 2023 apache-maven-3.8.8
drwxr-xr-x 9 root root 4096 oct 9 12:20 apache-tomcat-10.1.30
drwxr-xr-x 9 root root 4096 oct 9 11:43 jdk-17.0.5
drwxr-xr-x 12 root root 4096 jul 18 15:16 solr-9.9.0
root@debianmhr: /usr/java#
```

Renombrar las carpetas:

```
miahreyes@debianmhr: /usr/java
root@debianmhr: /usr/java# ls -l
total 20
drwxr-xr-x 6 root root 4096 ago 25 2024 ant
drwxr-xr-x 9 root root 4096 oct 9 11:43 jdk-17.0.5
drwxr-xr-x 6 root root 4096 mar 8 2023 maven
drwxr-xr-x 12 root root 4096 jul 18 15:16 solr-9.9.0
drwxr-xr-x 9 root root 4096 oct 9 12:20 tomcat-10.1.30
root@debianmhr: /usr/java#
```

Configuración de java, ant, maven, tomcat y solr


```
GNU nano 7.2 /home/dspace/.bashrc
fi
#####MAHR
#Configuracion de java
JAVA_HOME=/usr/java/jdk-17.0.5
PATH=$JAVA_HOME/bin:$PATH
JAVA_OPTS="-Xmx512M -Xms64M -Dfile.encoding=UTF-8"

#Configuracion de ant
ANT_HOME=/usr/java/ant
PATH=$ANT_HOME/bin:$PATH

#Configuracion de maven
PATH=/usr/java/maven/bin:$PATH

#Configuracion de Tomcat
CATALINA_HOME=/usr/java/tomcat-10.1.30
CATALINA_BASE=/usr/java/tomcat-10.1.30

#Configuracion de Apache Solr
SOLR_OPTS="-Dsolr.config.lib.enabled=true"
PATH=/usr/java/solr-9.0.0/bin:$PATH

export JAVA_HOME JAVA_OPTS SOLR_OPTS ANT_HOME CATALINA_HOME CATALINA_BASE PATH

^G Ayuda      ^O Guardar    ^W Buscar     ^K Cortar     ^T Ejecutar   ^C Ubicación  M-U Deshacer  M-A Poner marca
^X Salir      ^R Leer fich. ^\ Reemplazar ^U Pegar      ^J Justificar ^/ Ir a línea  M-E Rehacer   M-6 Copiar
```

Probar la configuración de Java, Ant y Maven


```
dspace@debianmhr: $ javac -version
javac 17.0.5
dspace@debianmhr: $ ant -version
Apache Ant(TM) version 1.10.15 compiled on August 25 2024
dspace@debianmhr: $ mvn -version
Apache Maven 3.8.8 (4c87b05d9aedce574290d1acc98575ed5eb6cd39)
Maven home: /usr/java/maven
Java version: 17.0.5, vendor: Oracle Corporation, runtime: /usr/java/jdk-17.0.5
Default locale: es_MX, platform encoding: UTF-8
OS name: "linux", version: "6.1.0-40-amd64", arch: "amd64", family: "unix"
dspace@debianmhr: $
```

Editar archivo server.xml

```
GNU nano 7.2 server.xml *
and responses are returned. Documentation at :
HTTP Connector: /docs/config/http.html
AJP Connector: /docs/config/ajp.html
Define a non-SSL/TLS HTTP/1.1 Connector on port 8080
-->
<!--Connector port="8080" protocol="HTTP/1.1"
      connectionTimeout="20000"
      redirectPort="8443"
      maxParameterCount="1000"
-->

<Connector port="8080" protocol="HTTP/1.1"
           connectionTimeout="20000"
           redirectPort="8443"
           minSpareThreads="25"
           enableLookups="false"
           disableUploadTimeout="true"
           URIEncoding="UTF-8"/>

<!-- A "Connector" using the shared thread pool-->
<!--
<Connector executor="tomcatThreadPool"
           port="8080" protocol="HTTP/1.1"
           connectionTimeout="20000"

```

Tomcat en ejecución

Home Documentation Configuration Examples Wiki Mailing Lists Find Help

Apache Tomcat/10.1.30

If you're seeing this, you've successfully installed Tomcat. Congratulations!

Recommended Reading:
[Security Considerations How-To](#)
[Manager Application How-To](#)
[Clustering/Session Replication How-To](#)

Server Status
Manager App
Host Manager

Developer Quick Start

[Tomcat Setup](#) [Realms & AAA](#) [Examples](#) [Servlet Specifications](#)
[First Web Application](#) [JDBC DataSources](#) [Tomcat Versions](#)

Managing Tomcat

For security, access to the [manager webapp](#) is restricted. Users are defined in:

```
SCATALINA_HOME/conf/tomcat-users.xml
```

In Tomcat 10.1 access to the manager application is split between different users. [Read more...](#)

[Release Notes](#)
[Changelog](#)
[Migration Guide](#)
[Security Notices](#)

Documentation

[Tomcat 10.1 Documentation](#)
[Tomcat 10.1 Configuration](#)
[Tomcat Wiki](#)

Find additional important configuration information in:

```
SCATALINA_HOME/RUNNING.txt
```

Developers may be interested in:

[Tomcat 10.1 Bug Database](#)
[Tomcat 10.1 JavaDocs](#)
[Tomcat 10.1 Git Repository at GitHub](#)

Getting Help

FAQ and Mailing Lists

The following mailing lists are available:

- [tomcat-announce](#)
Important announcements, releases, security vulnerability notifications. (Low volume).
- [tomcat-users](#)
User support and discussion
- [taglibs-user](#)
User support and discussion for [Apache Taglibs](#)
- [tomcat-dev](#)
Development mailing list, including commit messages

Instalación de postgresql 17

...

Cambiar la contraseña de postgresql

```
miahreyes@debianmhr: /home/dspace
root@debianmhr:/# su - postgres
postgres@debianmhr:~$ psql
psql (17.6 (Debian 17.6-2.pgdg12+1))
Digite «help» para obtener ayuda.

postgres=#
```

Reiniciar y crear el usuario y la BD de dspace

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~
root@debianmhr:/etc/postgresql/17/main# sudo systemctl restart postgresql
root@debianmhr:/etc/postgresql/17/main# su - dspace
dspace@debianmhr:~$ createuser --username=postgres --no-superuser --pwprompt dspace
Ingrese la contraseña para el nuevo rol:
Ingrésela nuevamente:
createuser: error: falló la conexión al servidor en el socket «/var/run/postgresql/.s.PGSQL.5432»: FATAL: la autenticación Peer falló p
ara el usuario «postgres»
dspace@debianmhr:~$ sudo -u postgres createuser --username=postgres --no-superuser --pwprompt dspace
Ingrese la contraseña para el nuevo rol:
Ingrésela nuevamente:
dspace@debianmhr:~$
```

Crear el usuario y la BD de DSpace

```
dspace@debianmhr:~$ sudo -u postgres createdb --username=postgres --owner=dspace --encoding=UNICODE dspace91
createdb: error: falló la creación de la base de datos: ERROR: la base de datos «dspace91» ya existe
dspace@debianmhr:~$ sudo -u postgres psql --username=postgres dspace91 -c "CREATE EXTENSION pgcrypto;"
CREATE EXTENSION
dspace@debianmhr:~$
```

Descomprimir el paquete dspace

```
dspace@debianmhr:~/software/dspace9$ unzip DSpace-dspace-9.1.zip
Archive:  DSpace-dspace-9.1.zip
1af2454045e41d0e8c414c4e9b9e61cba73593fe
  creating:  DSpace-dspace-9.1/
  inflating: DSpace-dspace-9.1/.codecov.yml
  inflating: DSpace-dspace-9.1/.dockerignore
  inflating: DSpace-dspace-9.1/.gitattributes
  creating:  DSpace-dspace-9.1/.github/
  creating:  DSpace-dspace-9.1/.github/ISSUE_TEMPLATE/
  inflating: DSpace-dspace-9.1/.github/ISSUE_TEMPLATE/bug_report.md
  inflating: DSpace-dspace-9.1/.github/ISSUE_TEMPLATE/feature_request.md
  inflating: DSpace-dspace-9.1/.github/dependabot.yml
  inflating: DSpace-dspace-9.1/.github/pull_request_template.md
  creating:  DSpace-dspace-9.1/.github/workflows/
  inflating: DSpace-dspace-9.1/.github/workflows/build.yml
```

Designar propiedades de instalación

```
dspace@debianmhr:~/software/dspace9/DSpace-dspace-9.1/dspace/config$ cp local.cfg.EXAMPLE local.cfg
dspace@debianmhr:~/software/dspace9/DSpace-dspace-9.1/dspace/config$ pwd
/home/dspace/software/dspace9/DSpace-dspace-9.1/dspace/config
dspace@debianmhr:~/software/dspace9/DSpace-dspace-9.1/dspace/config$ ls
config-definition.xml  ehcache.xsd                local.cfg                  registries
controlled-vocabularies  emails                     local.cfg.EXAMPLE         sfx.xml
crosswalks              entities                   log4j2-cli.xml           spiders
default.context.xml    hibernate.cfg.xml         log4j2-console.xml      spring
default.license        hibernate-ehcache-config.xml  log4j2-container.xml    submission-forms.dtd
dspace.cfg              item-submission.dtd       log4j2-handle-plugin.xml  submission-forms.xml
dstat.cfg               item-submission.xml       log4j2.xml                workflow-curation.xml
dstat.map               launcher.xml               migration
ehcache.xml             ldn                       modules
dspace@debianmhr:~/software/dspace9/DSpace-dspace-9.1/dspace/config$
```

Editar el archivo local.cfg


```
GNU nano 7.2 local.cfg
# NOTE: this URL must be accessible to all DSpace users (should not use 'localhost' in Production).
# It corresponds to the URL that you would type into your browser to access the User Interface.
dspace.ui.url = http://localhost:4000

# Name of the site
dspace.name = Repositorio de Miguel

# Assetstore configurations have moved to config/modules/assetstore.cfg
# and config/spring/api/bitstore.xml.
# Additional storage options (e.g. Amazon S3) are available in `assetstore.cfg`
# assetstore.dir = ${dspace.dir}/assetstore

^G Ayuda      ^O Guardar    ^W Buscar     ^K Cortar     ^T Ejecutar   ^C Ubicación  M-U Deshacer
^X Salir      ^R Leer fich. ^\ Reemplazar  ^U Pegar      ^J Justificar ^_/ Ir a línea  M-E Rehacer
```

Crear la carpeta de instalación


```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/software/dspace9/DSpace-dspace-9.1/dspace/config$ nano local.cfg
dspace@debianmhr: ~/software/dspace9/DSpace-dspace-9.1/dspace/config$ cd /
dspace@debianmhr:/$ ls
bin dev home initrd.img.old lib64 media opt root sbin srv tmp var vmlinuz.old
boot etc initrd.img lib lost+found mnt proc run snap sys usr vmlinuz
dspace@debianmhr:/$ cd home
dspace@debianmhr:/home$ ls
dspace miahreyes operador
dspace@debianmhr:/home$ cd dspace
dspace@debianmhr:~$ ls
Descargas Documentos Escritorio Imágenes Música Plantillas Público software Videos
dspace@debianmhr:~$ mkdir dspace91
dspace@debianmhr:~$ ls
Descargas Documentos dspace91 Escritorio Imágenes Música Plantillas Público software Videos
dspace@debianmhr:~$
```

Construir paquete de instalación


```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/software/dspace9/DSpace-dspace-9.1
[INFO] DSpace SAML 2 ..... SUCCESS [ 15.774 s]
[INFO] DSpace RDF ..... SUCCESS [ 1.518 s]
[INFO] DSpace SWORD ..... SUCCESS [ 4.741 s]
[INFO] DSpace SWORD v2 ..... SUCCESS [ 10.988 s]
[INFO] DSpace Server Webapp ..... SUCCESS [01:05 min]
[INFO] DSpace Server Webapp:: Tomcat deployable WAR ..... SUCCESS [ 42.157 s]
[INFO] DSpace Server Webapp:: Executable JAR ..... SUCCESS [ 8.210 s]
[INFO] DSpace Assembly and Configuration ..... SUCCESS [ 2.385 s]
[INFO] -----
[INFO] BUILD SUCCESS
[INFO] -----
[INFO] Total time: 10:15 min
[INFO] Finished at: 2025-10-13T13:00:50-05:00
[INFO] -----
dspace@debianmhr: ~/software/dspace9/DSpace-dspace-9.1$
```

Crear la BD y aplicaciones web de Dspace

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/software/dspace9/DSpace-dspace-9.1/dspace/target/dspace-installer
[echo]
[echo] * Make an initial administrator account (an e-person) in DSpace:
[echo]
[echo] /home/dspace/dspace91/bin/dspace create-administrator
[echo]
[echo] You should then be able to access your DSpace's REST API:
[echo]
[echo] http://localhost:8080/server
[echo]
[echo] =====
[echo]
BUILD SUCCESSFUL
Total time: 4 seconds
dspace@debianmhr: ~/software/dspace9/DSpace-dspace-9.1/dspace/target/dspace-installer$
```

Instalar aplicaciones web de Dspace. Copiar la carpeta server

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/dspace91/webapps
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace91/webapps$ sudo cp -r server /usr/java/tomcat-10.1.30/webapps/
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace91/webapps$
```

Configurar y levantar el servicio solr

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/dspace91/solr
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace91$ ls
bin config exports handle-server lib log reports solr triplestore upload var webapps
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace91$ cd solr
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace91/solr$ ls
authority oai qaevent search statistics suggestion
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace91/solr$ cp -r * /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/server/solr/configsets
cp: no se puede crear el directorio '/usr/java/solr-9.9.0/server/solr/configsets/authority': Permiso denegado
cp: no se puede crear el directorio '/usr/java/solr-9.9.0/server/solr/configsets/oai': Permiso denegado
cp: no se puede crear el directorio '/usr/java/solr-9.9.0/server/solr/configsets/qaevent': Permiso denegado
cp: no se puede crear el directorio '/usr/java/solr-9.9.0/server/solr/configsets/search': Permiso denegado
cp: no se puede crear el directorio '/usr/java/solr-9.9.0/server/solr/configsets/statistics': Permiso denegado
cp: no se puede crear el directorio '/usr/java/solr-9.9.0/server/solr/configsets/suggestion': Permiso denegado
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace91/solr$ sudo cp -r * /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/server/solr/configsets
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace91/solr$
```

```
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/bin
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/bin$ ./solr restart
-bash: ./solr: orden no encontrada
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/bin$ ./solr restart
*** [WARN] *** Your open file limit is currently 1024.
It should be set to 65000 to avoid operational disruption.
If you no longer wish to see this warning, set SOLR_ULIMIT_CHECKS to false in your profile or solr.in.sh
Sending stop command to Solr running on port 8983 ... waiting up to 180 seconds to allow Jetty process 2149 to st
op gracefully.
Solr will start in SolrCloud mode by default in version 10, and you will have to provide --user-managed if you wa
nt to stay on the user-managed (aka. standalone) mode.

Java 17 detected. Enabled workaround for SOLR-16463

ERROR: Logs directory /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/server/logs could not be created. Exiting
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/bin$
```

Solucionado:

```
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/bin
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/bin$ sudo chown -R dspace:reporas /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/
chown: grupo inválido: «dspace:reporas»
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/bin$ sudo chown -R dspace:dspace /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/bin$ ./solr restart
Solr will start in SolrCloud mode by default in version 10, and you will have to provide --user-managed if you want to stay
on the user-managed (aka. standalone) mode.

Java 17 detected. Enabled workaround for SOLR-16463
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8983 []
Started Solr server on port 8983 (pid=22336). Happy searching!

dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java/solr-9.9.0/bin$
```

Crear cuenta de administrador del repositorios

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/dspace91/bin
dspace dspace.bat log-reporter make-handle-config start-handle-server start-handle-server.bat
dspace@debianmhr: ~/dspace91/bin$ ./dspace create-administrator
Creating an initial administrator account
E-mail address: mighidalgor@gmail.com
First name: Miguel
Last name: Hidalgo Reyes
Is the above data correct? (y or n): y
Password will not display on screen.
Password:
Again to confirm:
Administrator account created
dspace@debianmhr: ~/dspace91/bin$
```

Mostrar tomcat/server

The HAL Browser Go To Entry Point About The HAL Browser Login

Explorer

/server/api Go!

Custom Request Headers

Properties

```
{
  "dspaceUI": "http://localhost:4000",
  "dspaceName": "Repositorio de Miguel",
  "dspaceServer": "http://localhost:8080/server",
  "dspaceVersion": "DSpace 9.1",
  "type": "root"
}
```

Links

Inspector

Response Headers

```
200 success
cache-control: no-cache, no-store, max-age=0, must-revalidate
connection: keep-alive
content-language: en
content-type: application/hal+json;charset=UTF-8
date: Mon, 13 Oct 2025 19:11:40 GMT
expires: 0
keep-alive: timeout=20
pragma: no-cache
transfer-encoding: chunked
vary: Origin, Access-Control-Request-Method, Access-Control-Request-Headers
x-content-type-options: nosniff
x-frame-options: DENY
x-xss-protection: 0
```

Front-end

Descomprimir node js en carpeta /usr/java

```
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java
ant jdk-17.0.5 maven solr-9.9.0 tomcat-10.1.30
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java$ tar -xvf /home/dspace/software/dspace9/node-v22.19.0-linux-x64.tar.xz
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/bin/
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/bin/corepack
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/bin/npx
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/bin/node
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/bin/npm
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/include/
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/include/node/
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/include/node/v8-platform.h
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/include/node/v8-local-handle.h
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/include/node/uv.h
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/include/node/v8-script.h
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/include/node/v8-debug.h
```

Renombrar la carpeta

```
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/lib/node_modules/npm/man/man5/folders.5
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/lib/node_modules/npm/man/man5/npm-shrinkwrap-json.5
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/lib/node_modules/npm/man/man5/package-lock-json.5
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/lib/node_modules/npm/man/man5/npmrc.5
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/lib/node_modules/npm/man/man5/package-json.5
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/lib/node_modules/npm/man/man5/install.5
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/lib/node_modules/npm/man/man5/npm-global.5
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/lib/node_modules/npm/LICENSE
node-v22.19.0-linux-x64/LICENSE
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java$ ls
ant jdk-17.0.5 maven node-v22.19.0-linux-x64 solr-9.9.0 tomcat-10.1.30
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java$ mv node-v22.19.0-linux-x64 node-v22.19.0
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java$ ls
ant jdk-17.0.5 maven node-v22.19.0 solr-9.9.0 tomcat-10.1.30
dspace@debianmhr: /usr/java$
```

Editar archivo .bashrc

A screenshot of a terminal window showing the nano 7.2 editor editing the .bashrc file. The terminal title is 'dspace@debianmhr: ~'. The editor content includes environment variables for CATALINA_BASE, SOLR_OPTS, and NODE_OPTIONS, along with export statements for JAVA_HOME, JAVA_OPTS, SOLR_OPTS, ANT_HOME, CATALINA_HOME, CATALINA_BASE, PATH, and NODE_OPTIONS. A status bar at the bottom shows '[139 líneas escritas]' and a list of keyboard shortcuts such as Ayuda, Guardar, Buscar, Cortar, Ejecutar, Ubicación, Deshacer, Poner marca, Salir, Leer fich., Reemplazar, Pegar, Justificar, Ir a línea, Rehacer, and Copiar.

Instalación de pm2

A screenshot of a terminal window showing the installation of pm2. The terminal title is 'dspace@debianmhr: ~'. The user runs 'nano bashrc', 'nano .bashrc', 'source .bashrc', and 'npm install --global pm2'. The output shows 'added 133 packages in 8s', '13 packages are looking for funding', and several npm notices, including a new major version of npm available (10.9.3 -> 11.6.2) and a changelog link.

Descomprimir angular

A screenshot of a terminal window showing the extraction of an angular zip file. The terminal title is 'dspace@debianmhr: ~'. The user runs 'pwd' (showing '/home/dspace') and 'unzip /home/dspace/software/dspace9/dspace-angular-dspace-9.1.zip'. The output shows the archive path and a list of files being created or inflated, including .codecov.yml, .dockerignore, .editorconfig, .eslintrc.json, .gitattributes, .github/, .github/ISSUE_TEMPLATE/, and .github/ISSUE_TEMPLATE/bug_report.md and feature_request.md.

Entrar a carpeta y ejecutar npm install

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/dspace-angular-dspace-9.1$ ls
angular.json      Dockerfile          lint                README.md          tsconfig.app.json  webpack
config            Dockerfile.dist    nodemon.json       scripts            tsconfig.json
CONTRIBUTING.md docs                NOTICE            SECURITY.md         tsconfig.server.json
cypress           karma.conf.js      package.json       server.ts          tsconfig.spec.json
cypress.config.ts LICENSE             package-lock.json  src                tsconfig.ts-node.json
docker            LICENSES_THIRD_PARTY postcss.config.js  startup-message.ts typedoc.json
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace-angular-dspace-9.1$ npm install
:█
```

Renombrar la carpeta dspace-angular-dspace-9.1 por dspace-angular91

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~$ pwd
/home/dspace
dspace@debianmhr: ~$ ls
Descargas  dspace91          Escritorio  Música        Público  Videos
Documentos dspace-angular-dspace-9.1 Imágenes   Plantillas   software
dspace@debianmhr: ~$ mv dspace-angular-dspace-9.1 dspace-angular91
dspace@debianmhr: ~$ ls
Descargas  Documentos  dspace91  dspace-angular91  Escritorio  Imágenes  Música  Plantillas  Público  software  Videos
dspace@debianmhr: ~$ █
```

Construir la interfaz de usuario

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/dspace-angular91
config            Dockerfile.dist    node_modules       README.md          tsconfig.app.json  webpack
CONTRIBUTING.md docs                nodemon.json       scripts            tsconfig.json
cypress           karma.conf.js      NOTICE            SECURITY.md         tsconfig.server.json
cypress.config.ts LICENSE             package.json       server.ts          tsconfig.spec.json
docker            LICENSES_THIRD_PARTY package-lock.json  src                tsconfig.ts-node.json
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace-angular91$ npm run build:prod

> dspace-angular@9.1.0 build:prod
> cross-env NODE_ENV=production npm run build:ssr

> dspace-angular@9.1.0 build:ssr
> ng build --configuration production && ng run dspace-angular:server:production

* Generating browser application bundles (phase: setup)...█
```

Entrar a carpeta dspace-angular91/config y borrar el archivo config.yml. Luego renombrar config.example.yml por config.prod.yml

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/dspace-angular91/config
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace-angular91/config$ ls
config.example.yml  config.yml
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace-angular91/config$ rm config.yml
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace-angular91/config$ ls
config.example.yml
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace-angular91/config$ cp config.example.yml config.prod.yml
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace-angular91/config$ ls
config.example.yml  config.prod.yml
dspace@debianmhr:~/dspace-angular91/config$
```

Editar el archivo config.prod.yml

```
GNU nano 7.2 config.prod.yml
# Angular User Interface settings
# NOTE: these settings define where Node.js will start your UI application. Therefore, these
# "ui" settings usually specify a localhost port/URL which is later proxied to a public URL (using Apache or similar)
ui:
  ssl: false
  host: localhost
  port: 4000
  # NOTE: Space is capitalized because 'namespace' is a reserved string in TypeScript
  nameSpace: /
  # The rateLimiter settings limit each IP to a 'max' of 500 requests per 'windowMs' (1 minute).
  rateLimiter:
^G Ayuda      ^O Guardar   ^W Buscar    ^K Cortar    ^T Ejecutar  ^C Ubicación M-U Deshacer M-A Poner marca
^X Salir      ^R Leer fich.^_ Reemplazar ^U Pegar     ^J Justificar ^/ Ir a línea M-E Rehacer  M-G Copiar
```

```
GNU nano 7.2 config.prod.yml *
# The REST API server settings
# NOTE: these settings define which (publicly available) REST API to use. They are usually
# 'synced' with the 'dspace.server.url' setting in your backend's local.cfg.
rest:
  ssl: false
  host: localhost
  port: 8080
  # NOTE: Space is capitalized because 'namespace' is a reserved string in TypeScript
  nameSpace: /server
  # Provide a different REST url to be used during SSR execution. It must contain the whole url including protocol, server
  # server namespace (uncomment to use it).
```

Crear la carpeta dspace91-ui

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~$ pwd
/home/dspace
dspace@debianmhr: ~$ mkdir dspace91-ui
dspace@debianmhr: ~$ cp -r dspace-angular91/dist dspace91-ui/
dspace@debianmhr: ~$ cp -r dspace-angular91/config dspace91-ui/
dspace@debianmhr: ~$
```

Levantar el servicio del front-end de dspace-angular

```
dspace@debianmhr: ~/dspace91-ui$ node ./dist/server/main.js
Building production app config
Unable to find default config file at /home/dspace/dspace91-ui/config/config.yaml
Overriding app config with /home/dspace/dspace91-ui/config/config.prod.yaml
Angular config.json file generated correctly at /home/dspace/dspace91-ui/dist/browser/assets/config.json

Environment extended with app config

dspace-angular
Version: 9.1.0
Environment: Production

[HPM] Proxy created: / -> http://localhost:8080/server/sitemaps
[HPM] Proxy created: / -> http://localhost:8080/server
```

Abrir el navegador con localhost en puerto 4000

